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Industrial Production in OECD Countries

It increased by an average of 28.73% between 2005 and 2022

Industrial production refers to the output of industrial establishments and covers sectors such as mining, manufacturing, electricity, gas, steam, and air conditioning supply. This indicator is measured in an index based on a reference period that expresses the change in the volume of production. The base year is 2015, i.e., 2015 = 100.

Industrial Production Index in 2022. The industrial production index for 2022 shows an interesting and diversified mapping of the industrial health of various listed countries. The top five countries — Ireland (181.9), Lithuania (154.6), Poland (151.2), Turkey (143.2), and Slovenia (131.5) — demonstrate impressive industrial growth. Ireland stands out significantly with an index above 180, likely due to a mix of business-friendly policies, massive foreign investments, and a strong focus on high-tech and pharmaceutical sectors. Lithuania and Poland show vigorous industrial activity, possibly reflecting the effect of economic incentives and a strategic position facilitating trade and manufacturing. Turkey and Slovenia, with their robust manufacturing sectors, may have benefited from strong domestic demand and increased exports. Countries like Korea, Sweden, and Finland (with values around 116.7 and 118.5) are in the middle performance segment. These countries are known for their ability to balance innovation and traditional production, maintaining a strong industry despite global challenges such as supply chain disruptions and economic fluctuations. Nations like Canada (107.5), Spain (106), and Italy (104.9) show more moderate increases. These countries may have diversified industrial sectors but could be facing challenges in technological renewal or international competition. Some of the most advanced and developed countries, such as the United States (101.7), Germany (96.8), and Japan (95.8), report the lowest indices. This might seem counterintuitive but could reflect a maturation of industrial environments with slower growth or a transition towards more service and technology-oriented economies. Additionally, factors like advanced automation and the offshoring of production might influence these numbers. Luxembourg (94.4) has the lowest index, which might indicate a lesser focus on industrial production or a more finance and corporate services-centered economy. These data, taken together, suggest diverse economic and industrial narratives. While some countries are rapidly expanding their production capabilities, others are in a phase of transition or readjustment to new global economic realities. Government policies, access to capital, technological expertise, market conditions, and international trade relations all influence the industrial production index.

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Industrial Production Index between 2005 and 2022. Countries like Ireland and Poland show extraordinary increases in the index, with percentage changes of 218.01% and 143.87% respectively. This might reflect a combination of foreign investments, government incentives for innovation, and robust overall economic growth. Ireland, in particular, has transformed its economic landscape, becoming a hub for multinationals, especially in the tech and pharmaceutical sectors. Countries like Australia, Austria, and Belgium have shown solid but more moderate growth, with percentage increases around 50%. These countries have well-developed industrial sectors that may have been able to sustain steady growth thanks to supportive industrial policies, the adoption of new technologies, and expansion into international markets. Conversely, countries like France, Japan, and Italy have seen a decline in their industrial production. Reasons behind this decline may include deindustrialization, international competition, structural problems in domestic economies, or a transition towards more service-oriented economies. In particular, the 19.81% decline in Portugal might reflect prolonged economic challenges that have limited investments and industrial growth. Luxembourg and Norway have shown significant decreases in their indices, which could be attributed to the highly specialized nature of their economies — Luxembourg in financial services and Norway in the oil and gas industry — making industrial production more sensitive to global market fluctuations. While India has seen an impressive increase of 109.34%, Japan has recorded a decline of 12.11%. These data reflect different economic trajectories in Asia: India continues to emerge as an industrial powerhouse with increasing investments and expanding production capabilities, while Japan may be influenced by an aging population and saturation in certain industrial markets.

Conclusions. The industrial production index value grew by an average of 28.73% for the analyzed countries between 2005 and 2022. Most countries had industrial production growth levels well above the average. Some countries had very high increases in the industrial production index, such as Ireland with +218%, Poland with +143.87%, and Turkey with +140.27%. Other countries experienced a reduction in the industrial production index. Among the countries with the worst results are Portugal with -19.81%, Luxembourg with -17.34%, Spain with -16.6%, and Italy with -13.8%. The variations in the industrial production index at the country level depend on a set of economic policies defined both nationally and internationally. For example, Poland and Ireland managed to attract foreign investments that increased industrial production, thanks to favorable tax policies. India attracts foreign direct investments in the industrial sector and is likely to replace China as the "world's factory," especially in the high-tech sector. Luxembourg might be a particular case, as the country focuses on developing a financial services economy and corporate governance supported by favorable tax laws, which may have reduced interest in industrial investment. However, it is very likely that European countries will also experience industrial production index growth in the future due to the trade war between China and the United States and the international tensions produced by the Russia-Ukraine war. Obviously, the re-industrialization of Europe is complex due to know-how issues, environmental legislation, and the insufficient level of digitalization found in many European countries, especially in Southern Europe. Rebuilding industrial production know-how while respecting environmental sustainability and growing digital skills is a challenge that Europe must face to free itself from dependence on international supply chains and rebalance the evident production imbalances generated in Pacific countries.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the

corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

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Appendix

Indice della Produzione Industriale per Paese nel 2022

Variazione Percentuale della Produzione Industriale per Paese (2005-2022)